

**Medium Stars with Big Attitudes:
Testing the Effect of Stellar Activity in the
Atmospheric Signals of Planets Transiting F-type Stars**

A Thesis Presented

by

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Abstract

While our ability to observe and characterize exoplanet atmospheres has grown immensely in the past decade, stellar activity continues to present a major barrier towards a clear understanding of transmission spectra. Notably, there have been three exoplanets around F-type stars (WASP-121 b, WASP-79 b, and WASP-103 b) with quiet photometric curves but radial velocity (RV) plots that indicate activity, revealing the potential presence of faculae. In this work, we explore how faculae can present a source of contamination in transmission spectra of F-type stars by modifying `SOAP 2.0`, a code that simulates the effects of active regions on stars. We compare the activity indicators (i.e. bisector span, full width at half maximum) observed in these three F stars to the values modeled in `SOAP 2.0` to determine if faculae can cause the activity observed while not appearing in the star’s photometry. We find that it is plausible for widespread, hot faculae to be present within observations of WASP-121 b, in contrast to prior studies that have rejected significant stellar activity as a source of contamination. We then explore the wide applicability of our method to other transiting exoplanet systems, focusing specifically on the case of TOI-1266—an M-dwarf with two planetary companions. Although stellar activity is historically not considered for transmission spectra around F stars, our results highlight a potential source of contamination that must be taken into account for other observations of transmission spectra in exoplanets around F stars. Further, we present a method that future studies can use to assess the likelihood that faculae are contaminating transit observations—which can be applied to any system with F stars or smaller.

Contents

List of Figures	iii
List of Tables	iv
Acknowledgements	v
1 Introduction	1
1.1 The History of Exoplanets, as viewed from Earth	1
1.2 Probing the atmospheric composition of exoplanets using transmission spectroscopy	7
1.3 The Transit Light Source Effect	10
1.4 A Focus on WASP-121 b	20
1.4.1 Discovery of WASP-121 b	20
1.4.2 Current Studies of WASP-121 b	21
1.4.3 Thermal Emission Spectrum, indicating a Stratosphere and Water Cycle	23
1.4.4 Future Research Directions for WASP 121-b	26
1.5 Overview of the Thesis	26
2 Modeling the Effects of Active Bright Regions on F Stars	28
2.1 Update to SOAP 2.0 to Handle Faculae	28
2.1.1 Theoretical Framework for SOAP 2.0 Adaptation	29
2.1.2 Confirmation that the SOAP 2.0 Adaptation is Effective	32
2.1.3 SOAP 2.0 Divergence with Stellar Rotation Period	37
2.2 Modeling All Possible Faculae Properties	39
2.3 Determining Which Faculae Properties Fit the Observed Data	41
2.3.1 Processing Observational WASP-121 Data	42

2.3.2	Statistical Analysis of Observational vs. Modeled Data	43
3	Results	45
3.1	Visualizing the Faculae Allowed by WASP-121's Observational Data	45
3.2	Contextualizing our Results	49
4	Discussion	50
4.1	Applications	51
4.1.1	Applications to Other Planetary Systems	51
4.1.2	TOI-1266 c	54
4.2	Future Improvements to Our Model	60
4.2.1	Spectra of Faculae	60
4.2.2	Updates to SOAP 2.0 for Fast Rotators	61
4.3	Conclusions	62

List of Figures

1.1	The “Pale Blue Dot”	3
1.2	An illustration of the transmission spectroscopy technique	9
1.3	The Sun with faculae and sunspots	11
1.4	An illustration of the Transit Light Source Effect	12
1.5	Photometry and radial velocity measurements of Kepler-21	13
1.6	WASP-121 b’s transmission spectrum	16
1.7	WASP-79 b’s transmission spectrum	17
1.8	WASP-103 b’s transmission spectrum	17
1.9	WASP-121 b’s transit light curve	21
1.10	RV measurements of WASP-121	22
1.11	Emission spectrum of WASP-121 b	24
2.1	A flowchart visualizing the workflow for this thesis.	29
2.2	Faculae intensity dependant on its distance away from the center of a star	32
2.3	Testing SOAP 2.0 adaption by varying T_{faculae}	34
2.4	RV, FWHM, and BIS SPAN outputs of SOAP 2.0	36
2.5	$v \sin i$ divergence in SOAP 2.0	38
2.6	Processed RV residuals for WASP-121	42
3.1	Two-dimensional histogram of our simulation results	46
3.2	Rejected faculae for WASP-121	47
4.1	As for Figure 3.1, but for TOI-1266 rather than WASP-121	55
4.2	Seasonal variation (temperature vs. latitude) for allowed faculae on TOI-1266	57
4.3	Seasonal variation (size vs. latitude) for allowed faculae on TOI-1266	58

List of Tables

2.1	WASP-121 Properties	40
2.2	Simulated Faculae Properties	41
4.1	TOI-1266 “Rejected” Parameters	59

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Two hundred seventy parsecs away from our Solar System, a planet orbits so close to its star that its atmosphere stretches towards the star, making the planet appear more football-shaped than round (Sing et al., 2019). While the planet is *just* far enough away to avoid being torn apart by stellar tidal forces, the intense heat and radiation from the star broil the planet’s atmosphere to a shocking 2358 K. This heat-scorched environment causes iron and magnesium to stream away from the planet, liquid sapphires and rubies to rain on the planet’s nightside, and an alien water cycle in which water molecules are constantly stripped apart and reforged (Mikal-Evans et al., 2022). All the while, the planet orbits its star on a nearly-polar orbit, almost a full 90° off from the expected alignment with the star’s axis of rotation (Bourrier et al., 2020).

The planet is WASP-121 b, the star WASP-121, and this distant and alien system is the focus of my thesis.

1.1 The History of Exoplanets, as viewed from Earth

Of course, our understanding of planets outside of our own Solar System did not begin with WASP-121 b, which was only discovered in 2016 (Delrez et al., 2016). Instead, we’ll begin this story on February 14, 1990. This was the moment that, from 6.4 billion kilometers into the vast expanse of deep space beyond our Inner Solar System, Voyager 1 aimed its camera backward and captured a picture of its birthplace: Earth. In grainy resolution, Voyager 1 captures Earth as a speck of light, smaller than the size of a single pixel, floating like a mote

of dust illuminated in a sunbeam. This picture, which has famously been titled “Pale Blue Dot” by Dr. Carl Sagan, epitomizes the fragility of human existence, and how we are nothing but a tiny speck floating through the vastness of space (Figure 1.1). While describing this image in his book “Pale Blue Dot,” Sagan says

The Earth is a very small stage in a vast cosmic arena... Our posturings, our imagined self-importance, the delusion that we have some privileged position in the Universe, are challenged by this point of pale light. Our planet is a lonely speck in the great enveloping cosmic dark...

It has been said that astronomy is a humbling and character-building experience. There is perhaps no better demonstration of the folly of human conceits than this distant image of our tiny world. To me, it underscores our responsibility to deal more kindly with one another, and to preserve and cherish the pale blue dot, the only home we’ve ever known. (Sagan, 1994)

Yet even this distant view of our home planet is taken from 6595 times closer to the Earth than the view that we have of our closest exoplanet neighbor, Proxima b (Anglada-Escudé et al., 2016). Aside from this discrepancy in distance, though, one can view “Pale Blue Dot” as the first time that humanity definitively observed a planet from outside its home system, and the first time that we humans sought meaning in these observations.

While “Pale Blue Dot” may have been the first of such observations, humanity soon turned our eyes away from home and towards distant systems. Just under two years after “Pale Blue Dot” was taken, Wolszczan & Frail (1992) reported the first definitive detection of a planetary body orbiting a star outside of our Sun¹. Wolszczan & Frail (1992) describe two planets orbiting pulsar PSR 1257+12—an extremely dense, rotating core of a star that went “supernova,” and speculate that these planets were formed from the debris left behind

¹It is important to acknowledge that Gamma Cephei Ab and HD 114762 b are two planets whose tentative detections were published several years before 1992—in 1988 and 1989, respectively (Campbell et al., 1988; Latham et al., 1989). However, Gamma Cephei Ab was not confirmed until Hatzes et al. (2003), and HD 114762 was later determined to be a brown dwarf (a small star) rather than a planet by Kiefer (2019).

Figure 1.1 The famous “Pale Blue Dot” photograph, taken by Voyager 1 on February 14, 1990. Earth is shown as a bright speck suspended in a sunbeam. (NASA/JPL-Caltech)

from the supernova itself. It was not until 1995 that Mayor & Queloz (1995) reported the first detection of a planet orbiting a Sun-like star, 51 Pegasi². This detection supported what astronomers had been speculating for centuries: that other Solar Systems outside of our own existed³.

From these first detections, humanity’s understanding of exoplanets blossomed. Before the end of the millennium, 16 exoplanets had been detected around main sequence stars, and that number rose sharply thereafter (Wright et al., 2011). As of April 4 2023, there

²Although 51 Peg is widely acknowledged to be the first exoplanet detection—Michel Mayor and Didier Queloz won the 2019 Nobel Prize in Physics for it—others have argued that the first *confirmed* exoplanet was HD 209458 b, which was observed during a transit event (Charbonneau et al., 1999; Henry et al., 1999). Until the transit of HD 209458 b, astronomers had only observed planets through RV signals—which report the minimum mass. Transits confirm the actual radius of the orbiting object, thus directly confirming that a body the size of a planet is orbiting the observed star.

³Giordano Bruno (1548–1600) was an Italian philosopher who predicted the presence of exoplanets. Bruno asserted in nine of his books that other worlds must exist, such as stating that there are “other planets and other stars, which are infinite; and that all those bodies are worlds and numberless, which thus constitute the infinite universality in an infinite space; and this is called the infinite universe, in which are innumerable worlds.” in his Third Deposition in Venice (Martinez, 2016).

are 5,322 confirmed exoplanets (NASA Exoplanet Archive). Amid the flurry of these first discoveries, it quickly became clear that many of these exoplanets were like nothing we had in our own Solar System; indeed, 51 Peg b, the planet discovered by Mayor & Queloz (1995), was a Jupiter-mass planet orbiting a Solar-type star with an orbital period of 4.2 days. Contextualizing this within our own Solar System, this is as if Jupiter were orbiting over *seven times closer* to 51 Pegasi than Mercury is to the Sun. This close-in gaseous type of planet later came to be known as “hot Jupiters,” and represents one of the beautiful and diverse classes of planets discovered around distant stars, the vast majority of which we have no analog to in our own Solar System.

The discovery of 51 Peg b and all other first exoplanet observations were made using the radial velocity (RV) method, which had been used in studies of stars for decades before being applied to the search for exoplanets (Mayor & Queloz, 1995). Radial velocity measures the “line-of-sight” velocity: essentially measuring the Doppler shift due to a planet tugging its host star back-and-forth as the two bodies orbit one another. This method was highly successful for detecting these first exoplanets because it does not require a specific inclination of the planetary system. Further, planets that are close to their stars and have a lot of mass—specifically, hot Jupiters—can produce RV effects well within the current instrument capabilities. As instrumentation improved and our catalog of RV-detected exoplanets grew, a second detection method was born: transits, with both Charbonneau et al. (1999) and Henry et al. (1999)’s simultaneous discovery of HD 209458 b. Unlike RV detections, one observes an exoplanet transiting by observing the brightness of a star. Then as a planet orbiting that star passes between the star and our line-of-sight, an observer witnesses a dip in the star’s brightness. This method requires the system to be oriented such that the planet’s orbital plane is in line with an observer’s perspective on Earth, and thus is less likely to be observed than RV detections. Although less statistically likely to be observable, the transit method provides key information on planet’s radius ($(R_p/R_s)^2$, where R_p is the radius of the planet and R_s is the radius of the star) and the planet’s inclination (which converts ambiguous

minimum masses found using the RV method into precise masses; Winn, 2014).

Beginning with the launch of the Kepler mission on March 7, 2009—only 14 years after Mayor & Queloz (1995) detected the first Earth-like exoplanet—the field of exoplanets dramatically shifted from individual detections to large-scale space surveys such as Kepler and TESS, as well as ground-based surveys like WASP (Borucki et al., 2010; Ricker et al., 2014; Pollacco et al., 2006). These surveys have collectively discovered thousands of transiting exoplanets, enabling the field to transition from studying individual planets to populations. Although we are just beginning to learn about the spectacular diversity contained within exoplanet populations, these surveys have given humanity invaluable insights into how planets form and how abundant these planets are. When humanity first looked back on our small planet suspended in a sunbeam 33 years ago, we did not know if there were any other planets outside our own Solar System. Now, we know that there are more planets in the Milky Way than there are stars (Cassan et al., 2012).

While we now know that our Solar System is not alone in the universe, we still have a limited understanding of the composition and habitability of most exoplanets, even those closest to our own. It is one task (and a challenging one in itself) to observe a tiny dip in the brightness of a star and detect a planet; it is another task entirely to observe the same brightness dip and know what the planet’s surface environment is like. These observations are so challenging that in the early days of exoplanetary science, most astronomers believed we would never reach the observational precision required to characterize the environments of exoplanets (Seager & Deming, 2010).

And yet, in what must be considered one of the true scientific marvels of the 21st century, the past decade has brought about the first true characterizations of exoplanet environments. Critically, most of this understanding relies on observations of each exoplanet’s atmosphere. The atmospheric composition of an exoplanet is a treasure trove of information that encodes a planet’s their formation, evolutionary history, current climate, and—in the case of terrestrial planets—habitability (Kreidberg, 2018). For this reason, the present and future of astronomy

points towards a focus on characterizing the atmospheres of exoplanets.

It cannot be understated how much observational precision is required in order to detect *any* atmospheric features on an exoplanet: observations of a star’s intensity change by a factor of 0.1% in the best case scenario of a very large and close-in planet, and this change in intensity drops to 10^{-6} - 10^{-7} relative dimming for terrestrial planets (Seager & Sasselov, 2000; Ehrenreich et al., 2006). In other words, we first measure the dip in brightness that a planet causes while orbiting in front of a star (a transit event), and *then* we measure how this brightness dip changes by a tiny fraction (0.1% - 0.00001%) of the overall light blocked. This is the resolution required to observe an alien atmosphere—and seeing these numbers, it is understandable that in the 1990’s, many astronomers believed we would never be able to observe the atmospheres of distant worlds.

It is thanks to incredible technological advances in space telescopes—namely *Hubble Space Telescope* (HST), *Spitzer Space Telescope*, and the *James Webb Space Telescope* (JWST)—that we now have the precision required to observe exoplanet atmospheres. Alongside the advances in instrumentation of the past few decades, several techniques have been developed that allow astronomers to pull back the curtains and peer into the atmospheric composition of exoplanets. While there are a wide range of methods used to characterize atmospheres, the most common and successful technique to date has been transmission spectroscopy, which is the observational technique that we focus on in this thesis.

As of 2023 we have observed dozens of exoplanet atmospheres, and we are only at the budding stages of understanding exoplanets’ environments and atmospheres. Our best observational precision is still far too coarse to measure the composition of an Earth-like planet around a Sun-like star, but we are getting closer to this goal. The successful launch of *JWST* on December 25 2021 has given astronomers access to unprecedentedly precise observations, and the very first exoplanet atmosphere results from this powerful observatory are just beginning to be published (e.g. Mikal-Evans et al., 2023; Greene et al., 2023). Comparing the field of atmospheric classification to humanity’s understanding of exoplanets as a whole,

knowledge of atmospheric classification is effectively where exoplanet population studies were in the early 2000s: the main techniques have been developed, but we are just beginning to reach beyond the easiest atmospheres to observe. In the coming years, the *James Webb Space Telescope* is expected to push the field to new reaches of understanding.

1.2 Probing the atmospheric composition of exoplanets using transmission spectroscopy

At present, the most common technique for probing the atmospheric composition of exoplanets is transmission spectroscopy. This technique was first proposed by Seager & Sasselov (2000), and can only be used on transiting exoplanets.

At a very foundational level, transmission spectroscopy relies on the fact that starlight can be split into its component wavelengths, which collectively forms a spectrum. To bring this example closer to Earth, imagine a beam of sunlight passing through a prism and splitting into a rainbow—the resulting rainbow is a spectrum of sunlight ranging through the visible wavelengths. When the starlight passes through an exoplanet atmosphere, however, the molecules present in the atmosphere block specific wavelengths (colors) of light—leading to what we call an “absorption line.” Different configurations of molecules present in the atmosphere lead to different wavelengths of light that are absorbed. The study of spectra is called spectroscopy, and is a critical tool that astronomers use to study the composition of objects in our universe. Spectroscopy is applied everywhere in astronomy from studying the earliest galaxies in our universe to characterizing comets in our own Solar System. Although spectroscopy is widely applicable, transmission spectroscopy was developed exclusively for studying the atmospheres of exoplanets.

To understand how transmission spectroscopy works, we must also take a small detour to also understand how the radius of an exoplanet’s atmosphere depends on which molecules are present. Atmospheres of planets don’t immediately stop at a defined boundary; every

molecule in the atmosphere “puffs” out to a certain radius, which is quantified by a factor known as a molecule’s scale height. Scale height is different for each molecule in a planet’s atmosphere, depending on how much of the molecule is present and how heavy the species is. The key takeaway here is that planetary radius changes as a function of molecular composition, and planetary radius is thus dependant on the wavelength that one uses to observe the planet.

Combining the concept that (1) planet radius changes for each atmospheric molecule, and (2) light is blocked at particular wavelengths when a molecule is present, we arrive at the process of taking a transmission spectrum. Figure 1.2, created by Alam (2021), illustrates this process. To begin, a planet transits in front of a star. At wavelengths where molecules in the planet’s atmosphere absorb light, the planet’s radius appears to be larger during the transit, causing the transit depth, $(R_p/R_\star)^2$, to be slightly deeper⁴. Depth changes depending on the scale height of atmospheric molecules, leading to a variety of different transit depths at different wavelengths. Finally, the observer pieces this all together by plotting transit depth versus wavelength (Kreidberg, 2018). This final plot is what we call a transmission spectrum (in this example, represented by the bottom plot of Figure 1.2).

While transmission spectroscopy is currently the most used method of probing exoplanets’ atmospheric composition, it requires measuring variations in transit depth with very high precision—at best, differences in transit depth between each wavelength is 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} for Jupiter-size planets, and this drops to 10^{-6} - 10^{-7} relative dimming for terrestrial planets (Seager & Sasselov, 2000; Ehrenreich et al., 2006). Ideal candidates for this technique have a high equilibrium temperature (T_{eq}), a low surface gravity, low-density atmospheres (e.g. hydrogen, helium), and orbit small stars—namely, hot Jupiters (Kreidberg, 2018). These hot Jupiters are the easiest targets through which we can understand the properties of exoplanetary atmospheres—including compositions, presence of clouds/hazes, molecular

⁴This is because at wavelengths where a molecule is present in the atmosphere, the planet’s radius is the actual “bare” radius of the planet *plus* the scale height of the molecule. When a molecule is not present, the radius appears smaller, because it is just the bare radius

Figure 1.2 An illustration of the transmission spectroscopy technique, from Alam (2021) (Figure 1.2). The top panel shows a transiting exoplanet with an atmosphere composed of different molecules in different colors, each with a corresponding scale height. The transit depth varies by scale height, as shown in the middle panel. The bottom panel shows the corresponding transmission spectrum, with each atmospheric component marked in its corresponding color.

abundances, Temperature-Pressure profiles, energy redistribution (atmospheric circulation) processes, and the presence of absence of horizontal winds—while also refining the technique for future work studying the compositions of smaller planets with smaller atmospheres (e.g. Alam, 2021; Lustig-Yaeger et al., 2023). Because hot Jupiters are essentially test beds for refining observational techniques, we spend most of this thesis (until discussing applications of our model to planets orbiting M-dwarfs in Section 4.1.2) discussing the spectra of hot Jupiters.

Although transmission spectroscopy allows astronomers to measure which molecules are present in an exoplanet’s atmosphere—especially in big, puffy planets like hot Jupiters—the technique is constantly being refined. At present, a large amount of the work done to characterize exoplanet atmospheres is actually focused on the complicated process of turning raw observational data into an accurate transmission spectrum.

1.3 The Transit Light Source Effect

There are two main sources of data contamination that must be considered when processing a transmission spectrum: (1) telescope systematics, and (2) stellar activity (Barstow et al., 2015). Telescope systematics represent all internal noise and instrument corrections that must be taken into account while processing observed data, and pipelines are often developed to help standardize data processing⁵. On the other hand, stellar activity can represent a more subtle and individualized source of contamination.

But how exactly does stellar activity contaminate our measurements in a transmission spectrum? In short, this technique relies on the premise that transit depth varies because the radius of the planet is changing relative to a constant flux from the star. The assumption of constant stellar flux is complicated by the fact that most stars are known to have surface activity, including sunspots and faculae (Rackham et al., 2018). Figure 1.3 shows our Sun

⁵Data processing and the development of pipelines is a critical field in astrophysics, and this statement is not indented to minimize the amount of time and care that goes into considering telescope systematics.

Figure 1.3 An image taken of our Sun in April 2014 by NASA's Solar Dynamics Observatory. Sunspots are visible as defined dark regions across the center of the Sun, while faculae are the small bright patches primarily visible on the limb. Many stars exhibit similar—if not greater—brightness heterogeneity on their surface. *Credit: NASA's Scientific Visualization Studio*

The Transit Light Source Effect

Figure 1.4 From Rackham et al. (2018). The left panel illustrates a transiting exoplanet passing in front of a star with surface activity (sunspots). While the spectrum of the stellar disk is typically assumed to be homogeneous, the actual spectrum (central panel) will be affected by the stellar activity. This inhomogeneity will lead to apparent variations in transit depth. The resulting transmission spectrum (right panel) will thus be affected by variations in transit depth.

with sunspots (dark patches on the surface), as well as with faculae (smaller bright patches, most visible towards the dimmer edges of the Sun). While much of our understanding of stellar activity is characterized by spatially-resolved observations of the Sun, surveys such as *Kepler* have confirmed that the Sun is not unusually active and that most stars surveyed by these missions (primarily F- to M-type dwarfs) also exhibit activity (Giles et al., 2017). Because the vast majority of stars have heterogeneity in their emitted flux due to starspots or faculae, it is often an oversimplification to produce a transmission spectrum by assuming a constant stellar flux, such as what was suggested in early works (e.g. Brown, 2001; Seager & Sasselov, 2000).

Generalizing this source of contamination, the *Transit Light Source Effect* is the term given to the effect that a heterogeneous incident light source has on observations of an exoplanet's transit (Rackham et al., 2018). Typically, this heterogeneity of the incident flux comes from spots and faculae on the photosphere of the star. The result on transmission spectra is that dimmer regions on the photosphere of the star (starspots) over-exaggerate

Figure 1.5 From López-Morales et al. (2016). On left, the light curve of Kepler-21, an F-type star, where red points show the light curve after variations have been removed. On right, radial velocity measurements of the same star, as well as residuals in which the orbital motion been removed from the RV measurements. After variations have been removed, the light curve does not indicate heterogeneity in the stellar flux, as there is limited scatter in the red points. On the other hand, the radial velocity measurements do indicate stellar surface activity because of larger scatter in their residuals.

exoplanet atmospheric features, causing the spectrum to present a positive slope towards the blue. In other words, the infrared planetary spectrum gets dimmer towards shorter wavelengths. In contrast, brighter regions (faculae) mask exoplanet atmospheric features and cause the spectrum to present a negative slope towards blue wavelengths—meaning that the spectrum appears to have a higher transit depth towards shorter wavelengths. The effects of starspots due to the Transit Light Source Effect are well characterized, and papers such as Sing et al. (2011) discuss methods to remove the effect of sunspots from the atmospheric spectrum. Faculae are less commonly accounted for, in large part because the effect of bright regions on the photometry of the star has lower contrast, meaning that observations of a star’s flux over time (photometry) do not show variability. While studies do not always account for faculae, we note that many works (e.g., Oshagh et al., 2014) do account for the effects of faculae on the transmission spectra of planets around M dwarfs.

At present, it is thought that in main-sequence stars larger than our Sun—i.e., F stars and hotter—there is typically no need to account for stellar activity when taking a transmission spectrum because photometric measurements of these large stars show no detectable activity. Although justifying the lack of stellar surface heterogeneity based on a lack of scatter in photometry is tempting, inactive photometry only excludes the presence of starspots, but does not exclude faculae. This is because faculae have low contrast on the surface of the star, so do not show up in observations as defined brightness heterogeneity. To make this concept more tangible, it helps to envision a lamp. If one were to draw a point on the lamp in sharpie, the dot would be visible. On the other hand, if one were to poke a small hole in the lamp (assuming the vacuum is maintained) the overall light would appear brighter, but the individual point is not visible. In this example, the sharpie mark is a sunspot and the hole poked is a facula—and indeed, starspots present themselves as dark patches while faculae simply make the region around them appear brighter. This reasoning is why we say that faculae have lower contrast than spots, and why they do not appear in photometric observations.

Although not detectable through photometry, faculae can be observed using radial velocity. This is because RV observations consider the star as two hemispheres; as the star rotates, one hemisphere moves towards the observer (blueshifted) and the other away from the observer (redshifted). Photometric contrast has no effect on RV measurements—as the hemisphere containing faculae moves towards the observer, there is a larger contribution to the blueshifted part of the measurement. Faculae are further pronounced in RV observations of stellar activity because they are associated with strong magnetic fields. These magnetic fields suppress convection around the active region, which in turn, suppresses the convective blueshift effect—in which rising convective cells make the spectrum appear blueshifted—in the stellar spectrum (Dumusque et al., 2014). Overall, faculae appear in RV observations due to their hemispheric flux contributions as well as a net redshift effect due to the suppression of convective blueshift.

Because faculae are observable through radial velocity measurements but through photometric measurements, observing heterogeneity in a star’s RV but not in its photometry is an indicator of active bright regions on the surface of the star. An example of a star with observed faculae is shown in Figure 1.5; Kepler-21 is an F-type star that shows no scatter in its photometry (left plot, red points), whereas it does show clear scatter in the RV residuals (right plot, blue points) (López-Morales et al., 2016). Kepler-21 was thus interpreted to have faculae on its surface, which goes against the community’s general belief that stellar activity does not need to be considered for F-type stars. As such, it is possible that there are other cases where the transit light source effect needs to be taken into account for the transmission spectra of planets orbiting stars larger than our Sun.

In particular, the transmission spectra of exoplanets orbiting three F-type stars (WASP-121 b, WASP-79 b, and WASP-103 b) have been observed that show a surprising negative slope towards blue (shorter than $1\mu\text{m}$) wavelengths (Evans et al., 2017; Rathcke et al., 2021; Kirk et al., 2021). All three spectra stated here are shown in Figures 1.6, 1.7, and 1.8, and the downwards slope below $1\mu\text{m}$ —and especially past $0.4\mu\text{m}$ —is of particular note. At present, we know of two possible causes for a downwards slope short of $1\mu\text{m}$ in atmospheric spectra: (1) faculae on the surface of the star that cause the transit light source effect, or (2) aerosols in the atmosphere of the planet which cause Rayleigh scattering. Atmospheric models based on observed species in each of the three planets discussed in this paragraph do not predict the presence of aerosols, but the stellar activity of these planets makes a tempting case for the contribution of faculae to the transit light source effect. In particular, RV measurements taken of the WASP-121 indicate activity, although the photometric curve appears to be quiet (Delrez et al., 2016).

Because the downwards slope towards blue wavelengths is unexpected in each of these three planets, prior work has been done to investigate the potential causes of this spectroscopic feature—including discussing the possibility of the transit light source effect, although each of these planets orbit an F star. In the case of WASP-103 b, Kirk et al. (2021) find

Figure 1.6 The transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b, from Figure 11 of Evans et al. (2018). The different colors of points represent independent observations (all from *Hubble Space Telescope*, except the grey squares). Two best-fit forward models for the spectrum are plotted in purple: light purple assumes TiO/VO opacity while dark purple assumes there is no TiO/VO opacity. The downwards slope towards blue wavelengths is particularly evident in the data points below $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, which have a much higher (R_p/R_\star) value than the plotted models (purple lines) predict.

Figure 1.7 The transmission spectrum of WASP-79 b, presented in Gressier et al. (2023). Observational data is from the Hubble PanCET program (red) as well as from Hubble STIS G430L and G750L data (orange and yellow; Rathcke et al., 2021) and HST WFC3 observations (green and blue; Sotzen et al., 2020)

Figure 1.8 The transmission spectrum of WASP-103 b, presented in Kirk et al. (2021). The authors present a spectrum further into the IR (towards longer wavelengths), which we exclude as this thesis focuses on spectral features below $1 \mu\text{m}$.

that the planet’s spectrum can be fit with unocculted faculae ~ 350 K hotter than the stellar photosphere and covering $22^{+9}_{-12}\%$ of the combined optical + IR surface—a temptingly reasonable value of surface cover and facular temperature. However, the authors do not rule out other potential causes for the downwards trend, including atmospheric composition (specifically, the presence of aerosols that cause Rayleigh scattering). Ultimately, Kirk et al. (2021) are inconclusive in determining what causes the downwards slope towards blue wavelengths in WASP-103 b.

On the other hand, past studies on both WASP-79 b and WASP-121 b have found that the downwards slope *cannot* be explained only by stellar contamination (Evans et al., 2018; Rathcke et al., 2021; Gressier et al., 2023). In the case of WASP-121 b, Evans et al. (2018) argue that the irregularities in the transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b are not caused by stellar activity because of: (1) the lack of activity in WASP-121’s photometry, (2) the lack of variability in transit depth epoch-to-epoch, and (3) Evans et al. (2018)’s inability to properly model the observed spectrum using unocculted spots. They instead continue their analysis assuming that the atypical transmission spectrum is due to the atmospheric composition of WASP-121 b. However, Evans et al. (2018) primarily considered starspots in this assessment, as opposed to faculae. While it is reasonable to discount starspots based on the work done in Evans et al. (2018), faculae could still be used to explain the lack of activity in WASP-121’s photometry but presence of activity in RV measurements—due to their low photometric contrast—and thus could also explain the observed negative slope towards blue wavelengths.

WASP-79 b contains the most thorough consideration of faculae as a source of contamination. Past work from Rathcke et al. (2021) considers the possibility of faculae contaminating WASP-79 b’s transmission spectrum, the authors find that the observed downwards slope in WASP-79 b’s spectrum could be by 15% of the stellar photosphere being covered by faculae ~ 500 K hotter than the surface temperature of the star—which is a physically reasonable value of faculae cover and temperature. However, the 0.2 - 0.4 μm data points that Gressier

et al. (2023) add to the spectrum of WASP-79 b throw this fit off, as the downwards slope is steeper than expected. Because of this unexpectedly steep downwards slope, Gressier et al. (2023) thoroughly consider how the slope could be caused by either absorbers (the authors consider MnS, Mg₂SiO₄, Fe, and Al₂O₃) and/or unocculted faculae. Gressier et al. (2023) find that none of the species considered provide enough absorption to cause such a strong downwards slope below 0.4 μm , and are uncertain as to what the main absorber could be. However, they follow a similar process to what Rathcke et al. (2021) did before the addition of the two points below 0.35 μm , and the updated study found that faculae on the surface of WASP-79 would need to have a brightness temperature of at least 9,000 K over 15% of the stellar disc—an unreasonably high temperature for a star at around $\sim 6,000$ K. Gressier et al. (2023) conclude while faculae may have a small effect on the transmission spectrum, the main cause of the downwards slope between 0.2 - 0.4 μm is due to an unidentified atmospheric molecule.

While the cause of the downwards slope towards blue wavelengths in the spectra of WASP-103 b, WASP 79 b, and WASP 121 b remains unknown, all past work has considered the potential sources of contamination from the perspective of the planet rather than the star. That is to say, no past studies have considered whether activity measured on the star could contain enough bright surface activity to cause the transit light source effect in the spectra of WASP-103 b, WASP 79 b, and WASP 121 b. As such, the goal of this thesis is to approach the effects of faculae on transmission spectra from the foundation of stellar observations, as opposed to computing the intensity of bright stellar activity that is required to cause a negative slope below 1 μm in each transmission spectrum (as was done in all past considerations of exoplanets around F-type stars). Our work is complementary to prior studies, as it provides a way to check if the necessary facular contributions to each transmission spectrum is physically realistic for the respective stars.

We specifically focus our analysis on WASP-121 b, because of the three planets discussed above, we have the most robust observations of WASP-121 (both photometry *and* RV data).

This is opposed to the cases of WASP-79 and WASP-103, where we only have photometry and limited RV observations. Having RV data allows us to (a) quantify the presence of faculae—the RV shows activity while the photometry does not, and (b) place a limit on how much activity is possible on the surface of WASP-121. Further, Evans et al. (2018) initially discounted the possibility of faculae as a source of contamination based on the photometry of WASP-121, leaving ample room for our analysis to reintroduce this possibility. Thus, the foundational goal in this thesis is to model whether faculae are plausibly constrained within the photometric and RV observations of WASP-121, and to provide a repeatable method that can be used to test other potentially active stars hosting transiting exoplanets.

1.4 A Focus on WASP-121 b

The previous section of this introduction justifies why we focus our analysis on WASP-121 b; in this section, we provide an in-depth review of the system’s discovery, properties, and several current areas of research on WASP-121 b complementary to our work.

1.4.1 Discovery of WASP-121 b

WASP-121 b was first reported by Delrez et al. (2016) based on a detection from the WASP-South survey. WASP-South is one of two arrays of telescopes that makes up the Wide Angle Search for Planets (WASP) program, in which arrays of robotic telescopes observe the entire sky for transiting hot Jupiters. First created when only twelve transiting planets were known, the WASP survey was designed to be a relatively inexpensive ground-based survey with the goal of discovering more transiting planets (Smith & WASP Consortium, 2014). Since 2007, when the survey began, it has been remarkably successful in detecting hot Jupiter planets—three of which are the exoplanets considered in this thesis (WASP-121 b, WASP-79 b, and WASP-103 b). WASP-South’s transit observations of WASP-121 b are presented in Figure 1.9. As the y-axis of Figure 1.9 shows, WASP-121 b causes the brightness of WASP-121 to

Figure 1.9 Figure 1 of Delrez et al. (2016), which shows observations of WASP-121 b’s transit light curve, taken by WASP south. On the time axis, zero denotes mid-transit.

decrease by 2% every 1.274 days (Bourrier et al., 2020).

In addition to being observed using the transit method, WASP-121 was observed using the RV method, as described in Section 1.1. The RV measurements presented in Delrez et al. (2016) are reproduced in Figure 1.10, and each point represents an independent measurement of WASP-121 taken using the CORALIE spectrograph, mounted on the 1.2 m Euler-Swiss telescope at the ESO La Silla Observatory. These 88 RV points were documented over the course of two observing seasons in the span of year and a half (Delrez et al., 2016). In this thesis, we include a more rigorous discussion of WASP-121 b’s radial velocity and photometry observations in Section 2.3.1, as we use both collections of observations in our analysis.

1.4.2 Current Studies of WASP-121 b

Transmission Spectrum

A year after Delrez et al. (2016) published their discovery paper of WASP-121 b, the planet was observed by the *Hubble Space Telescope* as part of the PanCET (Panchromatic Com-

Figure 1.10 Figure 2a of Delrez et al. (2016), showing the RV measurements (top) and residuals (bottom) of WASP-121. The x-axis represents phase between -0.5 (far left) and 0.5 (far right). The black line is a best-fit for the star-planet RV curve, and the dip at the center of the curve documents the Rossiter–McLaughlin (RM) effect, which occurs during a transit event.

parative Exoplanet Treasury; GO Program: 14767, PIs: Sing & López-Morales) survey. The goal of these observations was to observe the atmospheric composition of WASP-121 b using transmission spectroscopy. The first transmission spectrum was published in Evans et al. (2016) using the HST Wide Field Camera 3 in spectroscopic mode across the 1.12–1.64 μm wavelength range, with an analysis extended to 0.3–1 μm using HST’s Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph in Evans et al. (2018). The resulting transmission spectrum of WASP 121-b is reproduced in Figure 1.6.

In Evans et al. (2016), the authors present detections of H_2O , and the best fit model of a clear atmosphere with TiO/VO. Evans et al. (2018) then uses the more detailed spectrum to fit abundances to these molecules. Detections of H_2O give us an idea of where the planet formed, and whether it was within or outside the system’s water line (Öberg et al., 2011). Evidence for TiO and VO is also notable, as planets hot enough to have TiO/VO opacity typically have hot stratospheres with temperature inversions (Fortney et al., 2008; Hubeny

et al., 2003).

As we discussed earlier in this chapter, the spectrum of WASP-121 b is notable for the fact that it contains a negative slope towards blue wavelengths, which indicates either the presence of submicron aerosols or contamination from stellar faculae. While Evans et al. (2018) interpret this as scattering due to near-ultraviolet (NUV) absorbers (e.g. SH) in the upper atmosphere of WASP-121 b, it could also be caused by contamination in transmission spectrum due to the transit light source effect (discussed with more rigor in Section 1.3).

1.4.3 Thermal Emission Spectrum, indicating a Stratosphere and Water Cycle

Although this thesis focuses on transmission spectroscopy, other observational methods are less frequently used to characterize exoplanet atmospheres. In this section, we discuss the other techniques used to study WASP-121 b's atmospheric composition in order to present a more complete picture on the planet we are studying.

One such additional technique of characterizing an exoplanet's atmosphere is through its thermal emission spectrum. Thermal emission spectroscopy also relies on studying the planet's spectrum, but in this case through studying *emitting* rather than absorbing. Thermal emission spectroscopy is particularly relevant for planets planets such as WASP-121 b that have a thermal inversion layer, because these planets' blackbody emission spectra contain molecular emission (rather than absorption) features from the stratosphere. As such, measuring a thermal emission spectrum during a secondary eclipse can provide valuable information on the composition and structure of a planet's upper atmosphere. The emission spectrum of WASP-121 b is shown in Figure 1.11 (Evans et al. (2017), with more precise data updated in Mikal-Evans et al. (2020) and Mikal-Evans et al. (2022)).

Figure 1.11 Emission spectrum of WASP-121 b. Figure 2 from Mikal-Evans et al. (2022)

Stratosphere

Interestingly, WASP-121 b’s phase curve shows the clear presence of a stratosphere and thermal inversion on the dayside, indicated by H₂O emission. The results presented in Evans et al. (2017) represented the first time that an exoplanet clearly showed signs of a stratosphere, although stratospheres have previously been speculated to occur on highly irradiated planets (Fortney et al., 2008; Hubeny et al., 2003). These observations imply that much of the stellar radiation is retained at high altitudes, rather than permeating down to lower altitudes. Evans et al. (2017) speculate this retention is due to molecular species absorbing the radiation such as VO or TiO, as proposed by Fortney et al. (2008) and Hubeny et al. (2003).

Weather and a Water Cycle on WASP-121 b

Mikal-Evans et al. (2022) analyze both day- and nightside emission spectra of WASP-121 b, and find two shockingly different environments. On the dayside, WASP-121’s radiation is so strong that it strips water molecules apart, causing them to thermally dissociate. On the nightside, however, cooler temperatures allow water molecules to recombine. This process can also be applied to other species and can cause a process known as “cold trapping,” which occurs when refractory species condense on the nightside and sink lower, essentially removing them from the upper atmosphere on the dayside as well as the nightside. Mikal-Evans et al. (2022) find that species affected by this cold trapping include corundum, perovskite and Fe. However, Fe has been observed at the day-night terminator, implying that the atmosphere must have some vertical mixing mechanism that disrupts cold trapping (Sing et al., 2019; Hoeijmakers et al., 2020; Gibson et al., 2020).

Ultimately, WASP-121 b is a planet with two dramatically different hemispheres—a day-side that is heavily irradiated by its extremely nearby host star, and a nightside cold enough to condense refractory species. Because WASP-121 b is tidally locked to its star, the day side and night side of the planet are able to reach extreme temperature differences and intense

winds transporting material from the day side to the night side. This environment, where H₂O molecules are constantly stripped apart and reforged, presents a water cycle unlike anything we have in the Solar System

1.4.4 Future Research Directions for WASP 121-b

WASP-121 b is a prime target for the *James Webb Space Telescope* (JWST) due to its large size and proximity to its star. Indeed, Mikal-Evans et al. (2023) already present a phase curve for WASP-121 b, measured using *JWST*'s NIRSpec instrument. Phase curves are another method used to characterize exoplanet atmospheres, in which the heat distribution of the planet is observed. WASP-121 b's phase curve enables more precise studies of both WASP-121 b's day- and night-sides, and reveals that the nightside brightness temperatures are much lower than expected (926 ± 12 K between when measured between $2.70\text{--}3.72 \mu\text{m}$, and 1122 ± 10 K between $3.82\text{--}5.15 \mu\text{m}$). This indicates the possibility of an optically thick cloud deck blanketing the nightside of WASP-121 b. Ultimately, the phase curve from *JWST* enables new and exciting studies of WASP-121 b, and it is just the beginning of what we can learn from *JWST* observations. While the *JWST* transmission spectrum for WASP-121 b has yet to be observed/published, it promises to shed a more precise understanding of the chemical composition of WASP-121 b. This thesis fits well within the future of *JWST* observing WASP-121 b's transmission spectrum, because any interpretation of the transmission spectrum will also need to account for whether there is stellar activity on WASP-121 or not.

1.5 Overview of the Thesis

To determine whether it is plausible for WASP-121 b's transmission spectrum to be contaminated by stellar activity, we begin by adapting a method of modeling faculae on a star's surface. After testing and verifying this method, we apply it to WASP-121. We then conclude

this thesis by exploring other uses of our method within the field of transiting exoplanets.

More specifically, we begin in Chapter 2 by modeling faculæ using `SOAP 2.0`: a piece of software designed specifically to model RV and photometry measurements of stars with active regions (Dumusque et al., 2014). While the base-level code only models spots and does not provide the option of simulating bright active regions in the star like we need for this research, we modify `SOAP 2.0` to properly model the RV and photometry of stars with faculæ of different temperatures, sizes, and locations on the stellar surface.

After successfully modeling the effects of faculæ contained on the surface of WASP-121, in Chapter 3 we iterate through a range of facular properties (size, temperature, and location) to determine which combinations of properties are allowed within the observed data of WASP-121. We find that WASP-121 can contain widespread and hot faculæ, which is in contrast to the previous assessment of Evans et al. (2018), who claim the effects on WASP-121 b’s transmission spectrum must be due to atmospheric properties.

After delving into the specific implications of stellar activity on WASP-121 b’s spectrum, we discuss the broad application of our work in Chapter 4. Notably, the method developed in Chapters 2 and 3 has wider applications than just for determining the plausibility of faculæ causing contamination in transmission spectra around F-type stars; in Section 4.1.2 we show how our method can be used to investigate the interesting case of TOI-1266 c, an intermediate mass planet orbiting an M2 dwarf, whose transit depth has been observed to change between transit events. The application of our method to TOI-1266’s planetary system signals the usefulness of our method in studies of other transiting systems.

Chapter 2

Modeling the Effects of Active Bright Regions on F Stars

Because the goal of this thesis is to use simulations to determine whether faculae cause contamination in the transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b, this section focuses on the methods we used to model the changes that faculae produce in RV and photometric observations. In this chapter, we begin in Section 2.1 by discussing the adaptations we made to `SOAP 2.0`, a code that models RV and photometric signals of a star with surface activity. Then in Section 2.2, we discuss the process of running simulations of bright regions on WASP-121 using our modified version of `SOAP 2.0`. Finally, in Section 2.3 we detail the process used to determine whether there are simulated bright regions that are contained within the observed data of WASP-121. The work process for this thesis is shown in Figure 2.1.

2.1 Update to `SOAP 2.0` to Handle Faculae

The Spot Oscillation And Planet (`SOAP 2.0`) code is designed to model the photometric and radial velocity (RV) variations induced by active regions in a star—indeed, `SOAP 2.0` is a powerful tool for users who wish to input properties of a star (e.g. temperature, rotational period, and radius) and return models of what RVs and photometry an observer would record (Dumusque et al., 2014). `SOAP 2.0` is especially relevant for this project because it also accounts for the effects that active regions such as starspots and faculae have on these measurements.

The major deficiency of `SOAP 2.0` for this project is that while `SOAP 2.0` allows for the

THESIS WORKFLOW

Figure 2.1 A flowchart visualizing the workflow for this thesis.

user to vary the temperature of starspots, the code assumes a constant temperature for bright active regions (i.e. faculae). In other words, no matter which temperature the user inputs for a facula, SOAP 2.0 produces identical results. This limitation in SOAP 2.0 affects our work, as we seek to investigate whether *any* physically plausible temperature can produce the observed effects. Further, the set temperature for faculae in SOAP 2.0 is based on the Solar value—which is likely inaccurate for our purposes, given that WASP-121 is an F star and the Sun is a G star. However, it is unknown what the actual temperature of faculae on stars other than our Sun is due to observational limitations (we are unable to resolve faculae on stars other than the Sun). To get around this deficiency and run models for a range of temperatures, a large part of this thesis was adapting the SOAP 2.0 code to model a range of bright region temperatures.

2.1.1 Theoretical Framework for SOAP 2.0 Adaptation

Our understanding of faculae is tenuous, because we must base it entirely off of Solar observations. To make matters harder, even when only considering faculae on the Sun our

understanding of faculæ intensity is challenged due to a position-dependent contrast; faculæ have very little contribution to the stellar intensity in the center of the star where there is low contrast, but have a high contrast—and thus high intensity contribution—on the limb of the star. Additionally, there are large discrepancies in temperature measurements of individual Solar facula. As such, there are wide inconsistencies in the literature regarding facular contrast (Meunier et al., 2010). Because modeling faculæ is so challenging, facular intensity models are typically based on our observations of Solar faculæ, rather than attempting to adapt faculæ to different stellar types and temperatures. Indeed, in SOAP 2.0, Dumusque et al. (2014) used an expression from Meunier et al. (2010) to describe the temperature of faculæ on the surface of the modeled star:

$$T_{\text{faculæ}} = T_{\text{star}} + 250.9 - 407.7\mu + 190.9\mu^2. \quad (2.1)$$

Here, $\mu = \cos(\theta)$, where θ is the angle between the surface normal of the star and the observer’s line of sight (Unruh et al., 1999). Meunier et al. (2010) derive Equation 2.1 based on a model Solar intensity first proposed by Unruh et al. (1999), but apply this Solar model to other stars.

While this expression for the temperature of a facula does account for the limb-dependent contrast of faculæ, the expression also assumes a fixed temperature for a facula on the Sun. In the remainder of this section, we describe how we adapt SOAP 2.0 to model photometry, RV, and stellar activity indicators (FWHM, bisector span) for a range of facular temperatures, rather than just what was modeled for our own Sun.

To have SOAP 2.0 simulate the photometric and radial velocity (RV) variations based on the temperature of the faculæ, we begin with Equation 2.1. Because temperature changes with limb-to-center distance, we define $T_{\text{faculæ}}$ to be the temperature of the facula at $\theta = 5\pi/12$. This value was chosen as a distance where limb darkening is relevant, but is not extreme. At this distance from the center of the star, the temperature of the facula defined

by Meunier et al. (2010) is

$$T_{\text{faculæ, unscaled}} = T_{\text{star}} + 250.9 - 407.7 \cos\left(\frac{5\pi}{12}\right) + 190.9 \cos^2\left(\frac{5\pi}{12}\right) = T_{\text{star}} + 158.17 \text{ K.} \quad (2.2)$$

From here, we scale Equation 2.1 by a factor of the inputted facular temperature ($T_{\text{faculæ, input}}$) over the value found in Equation 2.2 ($T_{\text{faculæ, unscaled}}$), to say

$$T_{\text{faculæ, scaled}} = \left[(250.9 - 407.7\mu + 190.9\mu^2) * \left(\frac{T_{\text{faculæ, input}}}{T_{\text{faculæ, unscaled}}} \right) \right] + T_{\text{star}}. \quad (2.3)$$

Finally, we convert temperature into intensity using Planck's equation,

$$I(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda kT}} - 1}, \quad (2.4)$$

where h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength the blackbody is observed at, k is Boltzmann's constant, and T is the temperature of the emitting body. In this case, we adopt $\lambda = 5293.4115 * 10^{-10}$ m, as used in Dumusque et al. (2014).

Using Equation 2.4 in terms of $T_{\text{faculæ, scaled}}$, Figure 2.2 shows the relative intensity of a facula as its location varies by distance from the center of the star. Near the edge of the limb ($\theta = \pm\pi/2$), intensity is high relative to the stellar surface intensity because the limb is dark and so contrast is higher; near the center of the star ($\theta = 0$) the intensity is low because the facula has lower contrast. Notably, Figure 2.2 also demonstrates that Equation 2.3 successfully varies faculæ intensity according to an inputted faculæ temperature, while still preserving the limb-to-center contrast dependency of faculæ.

In summary, the implementation of this adaptation (replacing Equation 2.1 with Equation 2.3) works as follows: From the perspective of SOAP 2.0, the visible hemisphere of the star is divided into many small regions. If SOAP 2.0 recognizes a facula in that region, it will calculate intensity as $I(\lambda, T_{\text{faculæ, scaled}})$; if there is no faculæ in the region, intensity is calculated as $I(\lambda, T_{\text{star}})$. The intensity of the facula will depend on its latitude and

Figure 2.2 Intensity of a facula, normalized over the intensity of the star, as a function of theta away from the center of the star ($\theta = \pm\pi/2$ denotes the edge of the star, while $\theta = 0$ denotes the center). The temperature-independent expression used to describe facula intensity in SOAP 2.0 is shown by the dashed line.

longitude on the star, as well as the temperature the user inputs for a facula, while the background intensity (no active region) will be a standard blackbody at T_{star} . As a result of our adaptation, SOAP 2.0 can run simulations for any inputted value of T_{faculae} rather than only the fixed Solar value.

The changes described in this section were written into the `starspot.c` file of SOAP 2.0, and then implemented into the program using the `setup.py` file of SOAP 2.0. In any future publication of this work, we plan to make our version of SOAP 2.0 openly available.

2.1.2 Confirmation that the SOAP 2.0 Adaptation is Effective

While Figure 2.2 hints at the success of our modification to SOAP 2.0, this section is dedicated to ensuring that the temperature dependency we've written into the program produces

physically realistic results.

Photometry

To confirm that our adaptation correctly models the photometry (i.e. observed brightness) of a star with bright active regions, we plot the observed flux of the star with faculae over one full rotational period, while varying T_{faculae} (Figure 2.3). We do this for a fixed latitude (30°), longitude (180°), and spot size (circular, with a radius of $0.45 R_\star$), and for a star with the parameters of WASP-121 (Table 2.1). While $0.45 R_\star$ is a relatively large radius for the active region, we deliberately chose it to emphasize flux variations while testing the adaptation. Indeed, Figure 2.3 follows the trend we expected: varying the temperature of the bright region causes the flux to increase with progressively greater amplitudes for higher spot temperatures, while low spot temperatures (i.e. 50 K above the surface temperature of the star) do not have a detectable effect on the brightness of the star.

Delving more specifically into why we are confident that Figure 2.3 produces physically realistic results, we begin with the top plot of the figure. Because this top plot of Figure 2.3 is calculated for WASP-121’s inclination, higher temperatures of faculae (e.g. 300 K above the surface temperature of the star) are *always* above a relative flux of 1.00; this is due to the fact that we are viewing WASP-121 pole-on ($i = 8.1^\circ$, Table 2.1; Bourrier et al., 2020). Due to this inclination, the active bright region is always visible and therefore always contributing to the observable brightness of the star. Because WASP-121’s inclination represents only one viewing inclination, we also test SOAP 2.0’s photometry output for a star of WASP-121’s properties observed at an inclination of 90° , or equator on. We plot the results of this test in the bottom plot of Figure 2.3. The outputs for an inclination of 90° are also what we expect; at $i = 90^\circ$, the relative flux is 1.00 when the facula is behind the star, but higher when the facula becomes visible to the observer. Further, the “top hat” shape is particularly reassuring with how it changes relative to facular temperature—brighter faculae are typically not actually brightest at the center of the star, but but slightly closer to the edge, where

Figure 2.3 Testing SOAP 2.0 outputs with code adapted to account for varying the temperature of a facula by showing the relative flux over a single rotation period. Color denotes a facula at a given temperature above T_{eff} of WASP-121. Here, we adopt the physical parameters of WASP-121, given in Table 2.1. The facula is assumed to be a disk of radius of $0.45 R_{\text{star}}$, or 10.12% of the visible hemisphere. The top plot is for an inclination of 8.1° —the observed inclination for WASP-121—while the bottom plot is for an inclination of 90° . Phase represents one full rotation of the star, with phase=0.5 corresponding to the facula being at the center of the visible stellar disk.

limb darkening allows them to have higher contrast against the bright stellar background. This effect is further discussed in Section 2.1.

Because SOAP 2.0 produces the curve shapes and scaling that we would expect for different temperatures of faculæ, as demonstrated in Figure 2.3, we are confident that SOAP 2.0 produces physically realistic results for the photometric contribution of faculæ at varying temperatures.

Radial Velocity

In addition to confirming the photometric outputs of SOAP 2.0, we must also confirm the radial velocity outputs. To do so, we plot the modeled radial velocity of a star with faculæ with a varied value for $T_{\text{faculæ}}$ in the left plot of Figure 2.4. As in Figure 2.3, this was done over one full stellar rotational period for a facula with a latitude of 30° , a longitude of 180° , and spot size of $0.45 R_\odot$ (10.12% of the visible hemisphere), and for a star with the parameters of WASP-121 (Table 2.1).

Notably, as faculæ temperature increases we see that the radial velocity curve becomes entirely positive. This is exactly what we would expect physically as a facula becomes hotter, as faculæ have strong local magnetic fields that suppress the convective blueshift effect inside the radius of these active regions (Dumusque et al., 2014). This leads to a lack of blueshift on the surface of the star, and thus a stronger net redshift—which manifests as a more positive redshift curve. We expect this effect to be stronger for higher temperatures of faculæ, which will produce a brighter net effect on the redshift. Thus, the RV curves in Figure 2.4 follow the expected trend in convective blueshift suppression.

As Dumusque et al. (2014) discuss, there are also computational relationships that can sometimes be used to confirm the accuracy of RV modeling. For example, Dumusque et al. (2014) use the fact that the FWHM peak-to-peak amplitude of a facula is expected to be three times greater than the RV peak-to-peak amplitude, and thus a ratio of FWHM/RV peak-to-peak amplitudes larger than three indicates the presence of a facula. However, these

Figure 2.4 As for Figure 2.3, but for the outputs of radial velocity, FWHM, and bisector span at an inclination of 8.1° . Phase = 0.5 is once again defined as the moment that the facula is at the center of the star, relative to the observer.

relationships are all established for slow rotators with a $v \sin i \leq 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which means that we are unable to apply these laws here (WASP-121 has a $v \sin i \approx 12 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Regardless, we are comfortable with how RV is modeled while varying faculae temperature based on the how the RV curve depends on faculae intensity.

Activity Indicators (FWHM, Bisector Span)

In the center and right plot of Figure 2.3, we plot the simulated FWHM and Bisector Span curves for a star with varying temperatures of faculae. In summary, we see little change in both the FWHM and bisector span measurements while changing the temperature of faculae. This is, thankfully, also the expected result in response to a change in facular temperature. This is because FWHM and bisector span both represent changes in a star's Doppler shift. While the location of faculae will impact the Doppler shift, intensity will not. As such, it is reassuring to us that bisector span and FWHM do not change substantially when we vary facular intensity.

Because the photometric, radial velocity, and activity indicator outputs all follow the accepted physical trends for stellar faculae, we are assured that SOAP 2.0 is accurately able to model faculae at a variety of temperatures.

2.1.3 SOAP 2.0 Divergence with Stellar Rotation Period

When testing the adaptations discussed in Section 2.1.1 for a variety of inclinations, we observed that for a rotational period akin to WASP-121 (1.13 days; Bourrier et al., 2020), the maximum amplitudes of bisector span and FWHM diverged wildly. As shown in Figure 2.5, an observer viewing the star with a rotation period of 1.13 days at an inclination of 90° will return the bisector span’s amplitude to be on the order of 10^{15} m s $^{-1}$, as opposed to the expected range of 10^1 – 10^2 m s $^{-1}$ (the value of which is shown by the blue line in the figure). This limitation is written into the unmodified SOAP 2.0 program; we performed identical inclination tests in the original version of SOAP 2.0 and obtained the same result. The divergence of bisector span and FWHM were likely not highlighted in prior studies because Dumusque et al. (2014) developed SOAP 2.0 using the parameters of slow rotators (e.g. the Sun, with a rotational period of 25.05 days) while WASP-121 is a fast rotator given its rotational period of 1.13 days (Bourrier et al., 2020).

Physically, we expect that SOAP 2.0 is unable to handle high stellar rotational velocities while modeling for fast rotators’ bisector span and FWHM because the program overestimates line broadening caused by rotation. This, in turn, impacts the FWHM and bisector span outputs because these two values measure how wide spectral lines are. In this scenario, the lines appear to be fully flat and the program attempts to calculate bisector span and FWHM by dividing by the slope of a central line—horizontal this case—thus diverging because it divided by zero.

Thankfully, this effect does not impact our work with WASP-121. Stellar rotational velocity is expressed in SOAP 2.0 through $v \sin i$, which Watson et al. (2010) define as

$$v \sin i = \frac{2\pi R_{\text{star}}}{P_{\text{rot}}} \sin i, \quad (2.5)$$

where R_{star} is the radius of the star, P_{rot} is the rotational period of the star, and i is the inclination of the star. The $v \sin i$ of the Sun when viewed at 90° is 2 km s $^{-1}$. On the other

Figure 2.5 $v \sin i$ versus the maximum bisector span amplitude produced by SOAP 2.0 for a star with WASP-121's parameters (Table 2.1). This was plotted for observations at an inclination of 90° (blue) and 8.1° (orange). WASP-121 has a rotational period of 1.13 days, leading to a $v \sin i = 64.5$ km s $^{-1}$ (blue vertical line) if it were observed at an inclination of 90° , and 9.2 km s $^{-1}$ at an inclination of 8.1° (orange vertical line).

hand, the $v \sin i$ of WASP-121 at 90° is 65.4 km s^{-1} —more than a magnitude bigger! Because we observe WASP-121 inclination of $i = 8.1^\circ$, though, the $v \sin i$ we use in this thesis is 9.2 km s^{-1} .

In Figure 2.5, we compare the maximum bisector span amplitude for a given $v \sin i$ in the case of both $i = 90^\circ$ and $i = 8.1^\circ$. Based on this figure, it is clear that observing WASP-121 at an inclination of 90° would not be able to be simulated using our method, because WASP-121’s $v \sin i = 65.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ would cause divergent bisector span and FWHM values. On the other hand, at an inclination of $i = 8.1^\circ$, WASP-121 is comfortably within the range of expected bisector span amplitudes. Given the results of Figure 2.5, we are confident that the bisector span and FWHM amplitudes presented in this paper are physically realistic despite SOAP 2.0’s divergence with high $v \sin i$ values.

Although this work is not impacted by SOAP 2.0’s treatment of fast rotators, we include this section because it will likely impact the replication of this method for other fast rotators at an observed inclination greater than that of WASP-121. Indeed, we hope that the adaptation developed here will be useful to other studies of transiting exoplanets, and want to be extremely clear with the remaining limitations of the model.

2.2 Modeling All Possible Faculae Properties

Once the changes were implemented into SOAP 2.0, we iterated through the program while varying four faculae parameters: latitude, longitude, size, and temperature. The stellar properties used throughout the simulation process to represent WASP-121 are presented in Table 2.1, and the range of values for each faculae parameter we varied is given in Table 2.2. The ranges of latitude and longitude were chosen to span over the complete visible hemisphere of the star. On the other hand, the temperature and size ranges of the facula required more intentional thought. Meunier et al. (2010) raise the problem that there are large inconsistencies in the literature over the temperature of active bright regions due to

Table 2.1. WASP-121 Properties

Property	SOAP 2.0 var.	Value	Citation
Solar Radius	<code>radius_sun</code>	696000 km	Dumusque et al. (2014)
Stellar Radius	<code>radius</code>	1.46 R_{\odot}	Bourrier et al. (2020)
Rotation Period	<code>prot</code>	1.13 days	Bourrier et al. (2020)
Stellar inclination	<code>I</code>	8.1°	Bourrier et al. (2020)
Effective temperature	<code>Tstar</code>	6460 K	Delrez et al. (2016)
Linear limb darkening coef.	<code>limb1</code>	0.395	Bourrier et al. (2020)
Quadratic limb darkening coef.	<code>limb2</code>	0.141	Bourrier et al. (2020)

Note. — The parameters used to simulate WASP-121, which are inputted into the `config.cfg` file of SOAP 2.0

the fact that faculae vary in temperature from one structure to the next, and because the observed intensity is dependent on the center-to-limb location of the facula. Given this, Meunier et al. (2010) derive a value of T_{faculae} on the order of ~ 200 K above the surface of the Sun. To be conservative, we extended the possible temperature range of any faculae on WASP-121 up to 1000 K. Finally, we used a similarly wide range for size of the facula, allowing the circular facula’s radius to be anywhere between $0 R_{\text{star}}$ and $0.5 R_{\text{star}}$ (12.5% of the visible hemisphere).

Throughout the simulation process, we followed the initial assumption used in Dumusque et al. (2014) that all faculae are circular. We also assumed that there was only one faculae on the visible surface of the star. While it is likely that these two assumptions are simplifications—indeed, there are likely multiple faculae structures that are not perfectly circular—we were only interested in the net contribution that faculae make to the stellar signal, which neither of these assumptions should impact.

In order to iterate SOAP 2.0 through all possible combinations of our four parameters, we were initially limited by the fact that SOAP 2.0 is designed to run one combination of inputs at a time. To address this, we developed a python script and corresponding shell script that run SOAP 2.0 while also changing parameters within the range specified in Table

Table 2.2. Simulated Faculae Properties

Parameter	Start Value	End Value	Step
Latitude	0°	90°	10°
Longitude	0°	360°	20°
Size (Radius)	0 R_{star}	0.65 R_{star}	0.05 R_{star}
Temperature	0 K	1000 K	50 K

Note. — The parameters used to describe the simulated faculae. These are inputted into the `config.cfg` file of SOAP 2.0

2.2. We also adapted the original `soap2.py` program to save the amplitude of outputs we were interested in (e.g. flux, radial velocity, bisector span, FWHM) to a pickle file, in order to reduce the net data output. If we publish the code adaptations to SOAP 2.0, we will also include the program developed to iterate through large combinations of inputs to the program.

In this case, our simulations resulted in 43,890 total combinations of the four parameters, which we discuss further in Section 2.3.2.

2.3 Determining Which Faculae Properties Fit the Observed Data

Once the SOAP 2.0 adaptation produced all possible combinations of faculae with a certain temperature, size, latitude, and longitude, we then needed to determine whether any of these simulated faculae could produce the observed photometry, RV, FWHM, and bisector span amplitudes of WASP-121. In this section, we discuss the processing of the observational WASP-121 data (Section 2.3.1) and how we compare it to the modeled data (Section 2.3.2).

Figure 2.6 CORALIE RV residuals for WASP-121, adapted from Delrez et al. (2016). These data are from two seasons of observing, which we combine. The grey points are observations taken during transit events that result in the Rossiter-McLaughlin effect, which we exclude in our analysis.

2.3.1 Processing Observational WASP-121 Data

The radial velocity data we use for WASP-121 comes from the CORALIE spectrograph, mounted on the 1.2 m Euler-Swiss telescope at the ESO La Silla Observatory¹. The 92 RV points were observed between 2013 Sep 11 and 2015 Jan 12, and result in Figure 1.10 (Delrez et al., 2016). These data were processed using two different versions of the Coralie pipeline: DRS-3.4 for the first season of observing, and and DRS-3.8 for the second season. To use these observations, we combined both seasons and excluded all observations taken of the Rossiter-McLaughlin effect, which occurs during a planetary transit. We then preformed a 3-sigma cut on the radial velocity, FWHM, and bisector span residuals of the RV data in order to reduce any extraneous outliers. We found that all data were within 3σ of the each residual set, meaning that no data points were clipped. The resulting RV residuals used in our analysis are shown in Figure 2.6.

For the photometric data, we used TESS observations from three separate transit events

¹WASP-121 was also observed using HARPS spectrograph but only six datapoints were observed outside of a transit event (Bourrier et al., 2020). While we do not include these data, further studies of WASP-121 using this method may benefit from the additional data points.

(sector 7 observed on 2019-01-08; sector 33 observed on 2020-12-18; sector 34 observed on 2021-01-14). After removing the transits of WASP-121 b from each light curve, we stacked the remaining photometric measurements together. Then, we performed a 3-sigma cut on the stacked data. We began with $\sigma=0.00117$, and after 5 3-sigma cuts we were left with $\sigma=0.00115$.

The result of our data processing in this section was standard deviations of WASP-121’s RV, bisector span, FWHM, and photometry, which we then compare to our simulations in Section 2.3.2

2.3.2 Statistical Analysis of Observational vs. Modeled Data

Following the processing described in the prior section, we are able to compare WASP-121’s observational standard deviations to the amplitudes of RV, bisector span, FWHM, and photometry, produced by our SOAP 2.0 models. The goal was to find which faculae modeled by SOAP 2.0 produced amplitudes of photometry, RV, bisector span, and FWHM less than or equal to the scatter of observed photometry, RV, bisector span, and FWHM measurements. The reasoning behind these requirements is because if a modeled facula produces RV and photometric amplitudes less than the observed amplitudes, it is possible for that facula to have caused the scatter observed in the RV data. On the other hand, if the modeled contributions to the parameters are not big enough to explain the observed distortions in the RV data, then another effect must be responsible. Both “allowed” and “not allowed” thus faculae provide key information on the impact of stellar surface activity on transmission spectra, and in Chapter 3 we discuss the implications of both in the context of WASP-121.

Finally, to bring together our modeling work and the observed data of WASP-121, and to determine which faculae are “allowed” and which are “not allowed,” we performed a series of cuts to our modeled data. In these cuts, the range (maximum minus minimum) of each parameter (RV, photometry, FWHM, and bisector span) was compared to the amplitude

(2σ) of the observed data. Any facular configuration models that produced larger standard deviations for at least one of the parameters was considered “not allowed,” and could not be contained within the observational data of WASP-121. On the other hand, any facula that passed each of the four cuts was considered “allowed,” and may be present on the surface of WASP-121. The results of this process are discussed in Section 3.1.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Visualizing the Faculae Allowed by WASP-121’s Observational Data

After iterating through all possible faculae parameters in SOAP 2.0, we are left with 43,890 possible combinations of size, temperature, latitude, and longitude. We then pass these faculae simulations through the cuts described in Section 2.3.2. Of the original 43,890 combinations, we find 37,676 to be “allowed” within the observational data, and thus cannot be ruled out by the lack of activity in the photometry of WASP-121. These allowed combinations are shown in a set of histograms in Figure 3.1. On the other hand, we find 6,214 faculae to be “not allowed,” meaning that they produced either photometric signals or radial velocity signals that were too strong to be contained within WASP-121’s observational data. The rejected combinations are shown in Figure 3.2, which (as makes sense) is the inverse of Figure 3.1. In both of these figures, each subplot is a 2-dimensional histogram of the percentage of simulated cuts allowed or rejected by the observational data. In this thesis, we draw particular attention to Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2, as they both showcase the results of the simulations described in Section 2.

Focusing first on the allowed combinations in Figure 3.1, we can clearly see that only in a small fraction of pretty extreme cases are faculae not allowed by observational data: in particular, when the facula becomes extremely hot (remembering the context that Solar faculae are typically ~ 200 K above the surface temperature of the Sun; Meunier et al., 2010) and extremely large. At face value, Figure 3.1 clearly shows that extensive faculae are

Figure 3.1 Two-dimensional histogram representing the main results of this thesis. We ran SOAP 2.0 for WASP-121’s properties (Table 2.1) or faculae with a range of parameters given in Table 2.2. These histograms represent which fraction of faculae for the given parameter value are allowed in the observational data; 0.0 (black) means that no combinations are allowed, while yellow (1.0) means that 100% of combinations are allowed for the given parameter region.

Figure 3.2 As for Figure 3.1, but of every cut that did *not* pass our selection criteria, and was thus considered “not allowed” within the RV and photometric data of WASP-121.

plausibly contained within the observational data of WASP-121, and thus must be considered as a likely source of contamination in WASP-121 b’s transmission spectrum.

Figure 3.2 supports the idea that extensive faculæ are plausibly contained within the observational data of WASP-121: there are *no* modeled faculæ that are not allowed between latitudes of 50° and 90° on the surface of WASP-121, even in extreme cases of faculæ 1000 K above the surface of the star and with a radius of $0.5 R_\star$. These parameters for faculæ are unlike any that we have observed in our own Sun, but highlight the fact that extensive stellar activity can be contained with the observational data of WASP-121. This is directly in contrast of Evans et al. (2018)’s determination that WASP-121 b’s spectrum is not impacted by stellar activity due to the quiet photometry of WASP-121.

Aside from the fact that faculæ are plausibly present on the surface of WASP-121, we can also use these results to confirm that the method presented in this thesis works, and to show that it can be used in other applications in the future. To begin, both temperature and size (radius) of the faculæ follow expected patterns—the hotter and larger a facula gets, the less likely it is to be allowed in the observational data. This is because hotter and brighter faculæ will produce a larger signal. We see this in the two-dimensional histogram of size vs. temperature (the bottom left subplot of Figure 3.1), where all small and cold faculæ are observationally allowed, but not all hot and large faculæ can be contained in the observed data of WASP-121.

Latitude is also physically realistic, although less intuitive. Because we are observing WASP-121 at an inclination of 8.1° , it follows that faculæ located on higher latitudes (i.e. near the pole of their star) are always visible and faculæ at lower latitudes are only partially visible. Faculæ located closer to the equator, and thus closer to the edge of the star, will cause a much larger change in flux compared to faculæ that are always visible. Further, these faculæ located near the equator are seen towards the edge of the star in our perspective—and thus have a much higher photometric contrast. Consequently, faculæ located at lower latitudes are less likely to be in the observational data than faculæ at higher latitudes. It is

also important to note for future applications that this parameter will change widely based on the inclination of a star; at stars seen equator-on (at an inclination of $\sim 90^\circ$), we expect that faculae located near the equator will produce a larger change in flux than faculae near the poles.

Finally, we are reassured by the lack of dependence on facular longitude: because we iterate SOAP 2.0 through one full stellar rotation for each facula, longitude should have no bearing on the produced amplitudes.

3.2 Contextualizing our Results

Ultimately, Figure 3.1 contains two main results: (1) extremely hot and widespread faculae are not ruled out by the observational data of WASP-121, and indeed are plausibly located on the surface of WASP-121, and (2) that our method produced physically realistic results that can thus be comfortably applied to other, similar cases in the future.

Focusing on potential future applications, it is deeply interesting to note that in the case of WASP-121, we find that all 6,213 faculae rejected in our simulations was due to their photometric amplitudes. In other words, no faculae were rejected because their RV and activity indicator amplitudes were too strong. As such, we can see that the limiting factor of which faculae are “allowed” on WASP-121 is entirely the quiet photometry rather than the radial velocity data. This matches with our original observation that the RV data showed activity while the photometric data did not. However, for all cases of this method is still necessary to use both RV and photometric data, because if the star does not have surface activity then RVs will become a limiting factor as well. This case is further explored in Section 4.1.2, where we discuss a star with *quiet* radial velocity data—and find that many faculae are also not allowed due to their RV amplitudes.

Chapter 4

Discussion

In the past decade, the developing catalog of exoplanet transmission spectra has revealed a number of spectra with downward slopes that are not predicted in our models, and can be explained either by hot active regions on the surface of the host star, or by the presence of aerosols causing scattering in the atmospheres of these planets. Originally, the possibility of stellar contamination in planets around F stars was discounted given that F stars are photometrically quiet. However, we know from RV observations that F stars show stellar activity—just stellar activity with low contrast (i.e. bright regions), which is why this activity does not manifest itself in photometric observations. In this work, we tested the hypothesis that quiet photometry and active RV observations of WASP-121, an F-type star orbited by an ultra-hot Jupiter, can be explained by bright active regions. Our simulations show that it is observationally plausible to have extremely hot and widespread faculae apparent on the surface of WASP-121, which can, in turn, contaminate the transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b. Analogous work done by Lee et al. (2023) has detected magnetic activity variability in two F stars, τ Bootis A and v Andromedae A, which supports our result that active bright spots are present in the stellar flux of WASP-121.

The main conclusion of this work is that based on observed RV and photometric data, it is possible for F stars to host faculae that may contaminate the transmission spectra of planets orbiting these stars. The technique we developed to determine whether faculae were contained within the photometric and radial velocity observations of WASP-121 can—and should—be applied to other cases where a transmission spectrum presents a downward slope towards blue wavelengths. Indeed, the method described in Chapter 2 can be used in any

case where we find an exoplanet transmission spectrum with a negative slope towards blue wavelengths, and RV and photometric data is available. While prior studies investigating transmission spectra around F stars (e.g. Evans et al., 2018) have discounted the possibility of a heterogeneous light source, this thesis has proven the need for considering possible cases of the transit light source effect in the transmission spectra of planets around F stars—especially if the F star being considered shows no photometric activity but activity in radial velocity measurements.

Given that we have shown large, hot faculae are possible on the surface of F type stars, the next step of this project is to model the effect that this magnitude of faculae has on transmission spectra (as has been done in other works such as Gressier et al., 2023). In particular, it would be illuminating to determine the scope of faculae required to contaminate WASP-121 b’s spectrum, and whether this scale of faculae is “allowed” by our method. Although this comparison would be extremely illuminating, it has proved difficult to perform because we do not know how the spectra of faculae looks like—especially faculae in stars of spectral types different than the Sun. The lack of accurate facular spectrum models is currently an open issue that will require future work either by us or by stellar astrophysics experts. Gressier et al. (2023) also encountered difficulties while attempting to fit the effects of faculae to WASP-79 b’s transmission spectrum, in large part due to our inability to model stellar faculae. Regardless, attempting to fit the effects of “allowed” faculae on WASP-121 is the next step in this project.

4.1 Applications

4.1.1 Applications to Other Planetary Systems

While this thesis treats WASP-121 as a case study in investigating the impact of stellar activity in F stars, the method we develop here has the potential to be applied to a wide variety of other transiting planetary systems.

F stars

Here, we have shown that at least one F star (WASP-121) may contain active bright regions that contaminate the transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b. Because Evans et al. (2018) concluded that faculae could not contribute to the transmission spectrum of WASP-121 b, following studies of exoplanets around F stars (e.g. Kirk et al. (2021) of WASP-103 b, Rathcke et al. (2021) of WASP-79b) have also been cautious to claim that the rise in R_p/R_* towards blue wavelengths (i.e., shorter than $1 \mu\text{m}$) is caused by unocculted faculae. Given that this thesis has emphasized the possibility that WASP-121 b can indeed be contaminated by stellar activity, WASP-103 b should also be considered for the same possibility as WASP-121. Serendipitously, WASP-103 has a $v \sin i = 10.60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Bonomo et al., 2017), which means that our adaptation to SOAP 2.0 will work for this system as well. Further, Gillon et al. (2014) have published RV data obtained with the CORALIE spectrograph for WASP-103—although with less data points than WASP-121 has—so it should be reasonable to replicate our process for this additional planet. It would be particularly interesting to run our model for WASP-103 b, because prior studies (in particular, Kirk et al., 2021) found that the slope in WASP-103 b’s spectrum could have been caused by unocculted faculae $\sim 350 \text{ K}$ hotter than the stellar photosphere and covering $22^{+9}_{-12}\%$ of the combined optical + IR surface. This combination is definitively considered “allowed” on WASP-121, but we cannot know if the same is true for WASP-103 until we run SOAP 2.0 for this system.

Similarly to WASP-103, WASP-79 RVs have also been observed using the CORALIE spectrograph (Smalley et al., 2012). As such, it would be interesting to run our model for WASP-79 in order to determine how the faculae parameters discussed in Gressier et al. (2023) match the observed stellar activity. This is work we intend to do in the future—we were unable to do it in the time frame of this thesis because of constraints obtaining and processing the RV data of WASP-79. Additionally, WASP-79 has a $v \sin i$ value of 19.10 km s^{-1} (Bonomo et al., 2017). Given that WASP-79 b is on a nearly polar orbit and the sky-projected spin-orbit angle is estimated to be $\lambda = -106^{+19}_{-13}^\circ$, we are likely observing the

star nearly pole on (Addison et al., 2013). Referencing Figure 2.5, we can see that SOAP 2.0 is likely to also work with a $v \sin i$ value of 19.10 km s^{-1} at this inclination. However, a test run would be needed to confirm that WASP-79 can be studied using our method.

Other Stellar Types

While this thesis focuses on planets orbiting F-type stars, the method we develop can be applied to any stellar type smaller than our Sun as well—and in the coming section, we show a specific case where the method developed in this thesis is applicable for an M dwarf system. Unlike for F-type stars, it is generally agreed that stellar activity can contaminate transmission spectra of Sun-like stars and stars smaller than our Sun (Rackham et al., 2018). Further, the smaller the star is, the more we expect its atmosphere to be covered by spots and faculae. This effect is particularly relevant due to the current interest in M dwarfs: because M dwarfs are so small, it is possible to begin using *JWST* to measure the transmission spectra of terrestrial planets around these stars. This will provide critical information on atmospheric retention of planets around M dwarfs, which will help inform our understanding of whether planets around M dwarfs are likely to be habitable. Rackham et al. (2018) have already preformed significant amounts of work towards understanding and accounting for the transit light source effect in M dwarfs. However, it is possible that the method presented in this thesis can supplement the work done in Rackham et al. (2018) and help to provide better constraints on stellar flux heterogeneity in the transmission spectra of planets around M dwarfs.

When discussing how our method can be applied to other stellar types, it is important to consider how the results will differ according to each system’s varying properties. In particular, our results for WASP-121 are shaped by the observer’s inclination to the star—nearly pole-on ($i = 8.1^\circ$), in the case of WASP-121. As we discuss in Section 3.1, under the assumption that faculae remain at a fixed latitude, the pole-on inclination causes faculae to be *always* be visible over the full rotation of the star. As a result of this, faculae have

limited contribution to variations in the stellar flux. On the other hand, stars that are viewed equator-on experience large amplitude changes in their photometry over one full stellar rotational period, because regardless of latitude the faculae passes behind the star for half of the rotation. This concept is well expressed by Figure 2.3. Further, the amplitude of RV variation from faculae also scales as $\sin i$. As such, faculae produce less RV heterogeneity due to stellar rotation the less they are observed to be rotating—so a faculae on the pole has no net effect on RV variations, because it remains fixed in location. Ultimately, equator-on stars are less able to have large faculae allowed by their data (both RV and photometry) than pole-on stars.

Looking towards future applications of this method, stars are most likely to have allowed faculae if they are viewed at low stellar inclinations and/or with limited activity in the photometry, as well as with high RV scatter.

4.1.2 TOI-1266 c

As has repeatably come up in the current chapter, the process developed in this senior thesis has potential applications in the field of exoplanet characterization, beyond only being used to research hot Jupiters orbiting F-type stars. Indeed, our method is currently being applied to the study of TOI-1266—an M2 star with two transiting planets. TOI-1266 b is a sub-Neptune-sized planet orbiting at a period of 10.2 days, while TOI-1266 c is an intermediate-sized planet with a period of 18.8 days (Demory et al., 2020; Stefánsson et al., 2020)¹.

Oddly, TOI-1266 c’s transit depth changes between different transit events while TOI-1266 b’s transit depth remains constant. One relevant piece of information for this system, potentially in line with the changing transit depth, is that TOI-1266 b’s impact parameter ($b = 0.43^{+0.12}_{-0.16}$) is significantly offset from TOI-1266 c’s impact parameter ($b = 0.714^{+0.050}_{-0.035}$;

¹TOI-1266 is a particularly interesting system because it represents a rare case where the higher-mass planet—TOI-1266 b, a sub-Neptune—is closer to its star than the lower mass planet, TOI-1266 c. Systems like this challenge current models of planetary formation and potential migration, and thus deserve special attention.

Allowed Plage, Season 3

Figure 4.1 As for Figure 3.1, but for TOI-1266 rather than WASP-121. We ran SOAP 2.0 for $P_{\text{rot}} = 32$ days, $T_{\text{star}} = 3600$ K, $R_{\text{star}} = 0.42 R_{\odot}$, and $i = 89.23^{\circ}$. Color corresponds to the fraction of SOAP 2.0 configurations that are allowed—0.0 (black) means that no combinations are allowed, while yellow (1.0) means that 100% of combinations are allowed for the given parameter box.

Stefánsson et al., 2020)². Physically, the offset in impact parameters between the two planets means that we are not observing TOI-1266 b and TOI-1266 c’s transits passing over the same region of the star. Given this, one proposed cause of the change in TOI-1266 c’s transit depth is that TOI-1266 c transits over a bright active region on TOI-1266, while TOI-1266 b’s transit path does not occult the active region. Within this hypothesis, TOI-1266 c’s transit depth changes season by season because the hot active region changes location, size, and/or intensity.

To test this hypothesis, we used our adapted version of *SOAP 2.0* and followed a similar procedure to our analysis of WASP-121 b. We began by processing TESS photometry and RV data (RV residuals, bisector span, and FWHM) of TOI-1266. After performing a 3-sigma clip on the data, we calculated the RMS of each parameter. Unlike in our treatment of WASP-121 b, we repeated this process separately for all four of the RV observing seasons; this way, we could see whether the possible stellar activity of TOI-1266 changed between observing seasons.

We then ran *SOAP 2.0* for TOI-1266, adopting $T_{\text{star}} = 3600$ K, $R_{\text{star}} = 0.42 R_{\odot}$, and $i = 89.23^{\circ}$ from Stefánsson et al. (2020). We assumed $P_{\text{rot}} = 32$ days, based on tentative P_{rot} signals in the periodogram of the RV data. Although only tentative, we were comfortable adopting this rotational period because it is in line with the average rotational period of an M2 star (30 days; from Figure 14 of McQuillan et al., 2013). Like in our analysis of WASP-121, we then iterated *SOAP 2.0* through the parameter ranges presented in Table 2.2. After running *SOAP 2.0* through the given parameter ranges, we passed all 43,890 faculae simulations through the cuts described in Section 2.3.2. As a reminder, these cuts compare the RMS of TOI-1266’s observed photometry, RV residuals, FWHM, and bisector span to the simulated values from *SOAP 2.0*. Based on these cuts, the resulting figure of “allowed” faculae combinations is shown in Figure 4.1. Because we repeated this process for

²Impact parameter (b) refers to the perpendicular distance from the center diameter of a circle to the actual path of transit, where $b=0$ is a transit along the full diameter of the star, and $b=1$ is a transit covering only the top edge of a star. In essence, this parameter documents how close the planet passes to the center of the star’s disk.

Figure 4.2 Allowed faculae for TOI-1266, split into the four RV observing seasons. In this figure, we specifically compare faculae temperature to latitude on TOI-1266.

all four RV observing seasons of TOI-1266, Figure 4.1 represents the results for only one of the seasons (season 3, arbitrarily chosen).

Because we were interested to test the hypothesis of whether TOI-1266’s activity changes between observing seasons, we can compare the allowed faculae from each season. Figure 4.2 shows one such comparison; in this case, we compare the latitude versus temperature subplot of 4.1. We also plot latitude versus faculae radius in Figure 4.3. These two comparisons are of particular interest because we want to know whether it is possible for either the size and/or the intensity of bright active regions to be changing season by season. Looking at Figures 4.2 and 4.3, observing season 3 appears more active than the rest, and season 4 is

Figure 4.3 As for Figure 4.2, but comparing seasonal variation in faculae radius versus latitude.

notably the least active. Although the changes between each season appear small, we believe that the results found here do not eliminate the possibility that TOI-1266 c’s transit depth changes due to stellar activity. Indeed, our results suggest that faculae are most likely to be present close to TOI-1266’s pole. This gives more weight to the hypothesis that TOI-1266 c is occulting an active bright region that TOI-1266 b does not pass over, given that we observe TOI-1266 c transiting closer to the star’s pole than TOI-1266 b.

The next step in using our adapted version of SOAP 2.0 to test the changing transit depth of TOI-1266 c is to compare our seasonal variability results (i.e. that season 3 is the most active, and season 4 is the least active) to the seasonal changes in transit depth. If bright

Table 4.1. TOI-1266 “Rejected” Parameters

Season	RV	FWHM	Bisector Span	Photometry
1	27417	0	11001	25251
2	26106	10203	0	25251
3	26106	26436	16359	25251
4	25908	27189	18423	25251

Note. — How many cuts of simulated faculæ (out of the 43,890 faculæ combinations) are *not* allowed because they have a bigger RMS than the RMS of the observed parameter.

active regions are the cause of TOI-1266 c’s changing transit depth, then we expect that transit depth will be the smallest in season 3 and largest in season 4. Seasons with more activity will have smaller transit depths because occulting a facula will cause additional background light from the star, making $(R_p/R_\star)^2$ a smaller value. The comparison between our analysis with SOAP 2.0 was done blindly to the transit depth information so that our results were not biased. Regardless of whether we find that TOI-1266 c’s transit depth varies due to occulted faculæ near the pole of TOI-1266, this discussion shows the wide range of applicability that the methods developed in this thesis have in the field of exoplanet characterization.

Focusing back on the context of developing the methods presented in this thesis, TOI-1266 also presents evidence on why we need both photometric and radial velocity data to constrain stellar activity. Indeed, we see that photometric variation is not the only limiting factor for faculæ on TOI-1266—unlike in the case of WASP-121. Table 4.1 presents the number of possible faculæ combinations that are considered “not allowed” because their simulated RMS is greater than the observed RMS. We show this for each season. Notably, these cuts demonstrate why it is critical to have both RV and photometric constraints for determining where faculæ are allowed; in the case of WASP-121 the only constraining factor was photometry, but here radial velocity observations and activity indicators (bisector span,

FWHM) serve as an additional limiter.

It is also interesting to consider TOI-1266 as an case where we apply our method to a star seen equator-on, rather than pole-on. As expected, faculæ are less likely to be observed towards the equator of TOI-1266, where they will produce more pronounced photometric heterogeneity. The results continue to follow other expected trends that we have previously discussed (e.g. smaller, dimmer faculæ are more likely to be allowed than large, bright faculæ) and thus reassure us that the adapted version of SOAP 2.0 works for equator-on stars.

Altogether, the case of TOI-1266 c is an example of how our method is currently applicable for use in other exoplanet systems, even beyond the direct applications of transmission spectroscopy. It also highlights the importance of using both radial velocity and photometric observations to constrain the effect of stellar activity on transit observations, and serves as another confirmation of the model developed in this thesis.

4.2 Future Improvements to Our Model

While the method established by this thesis provides a practical tool to determine the effect of stellar activity on transmission spectra, there are several areas that can be improved upon to make this tool more accurate and more widely applicable to different transiting planetary systems.

4.2.1 Spectra of Faculæ

In this thesis, we assume that active bright regions emit as stellar blackbodies. Studies such as Labonte (1986) have established that this is not quite accurate—faculæ exhibit weakened spectral lines, for example—but at present, no models of stellar faculæ have been made for widespread use. We also have few constraints for the temperature of faculæ aside from our observations of faculæ on the Sun; more advanced models would also allow for a better

idea of which faculæ temperatures used in our modeling are physically realistic or not. The lack of facular models has recently been shown as a limitation in Gressier et al. (2023)’s work on WASP-79 b, and we expect it to be similarly limiting in the case of WASP-121 b. Ultimately, future work to create accurate models of facular spectra would enable the field of transmission spectroscopy to better account for the contamination caused by active bright regions.

4.2.2 Updates to SOAP 2.0 for Fast Rotators

In order to apply this method to other planetary systems, the biggest constraint is that SOAP 2.0 becomes inaccurate for fast rotators; i.e. stars with a $v \sin i \geq 12 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. As discussed in Section 2.1.3, SOAP 2.0 was created to work for slow rotators—stars the size of our Sun and smaller—while F stars and larger are generally considered fast rotators. Our work in Figure 2.5 shows that WASP-121 is still modeled accurately by our method because we are viewing the star nearly pole-on, at an inclination of $i = 8.1^\circ$. However, if we were to view WASP-121 at $i = 90^\circ$, the stellar $v \sin i$ would be 65.4 km s^{-1} , and thus not viable for use using the methods presented in this thesis. Further, WASP-121’s rotation period is not atypical for F stars—Figure 2 of McQuillan et al. (2014) shows that the distribution of F star rotation periods is generally between 0 - 5 days. As such, the method developed here is not yet applicable for all F stars.

In order for our method to be widely applicable for use in considering the possible activity of F stars, SOAP 2.0 needs to be updated to model fast rotators. If this is not feasible, it is also possible for the method developed in this thesis to be applied using a different stellar activity simulator such as StarSim, although we have not yet looked into this possibility ourselves (Herrero et al., 2016). Ultimately, the method we present in this thesis is currently limited to F-type stars with slower rotations and/or low observational inclination angles, as well as to most stars—regardless of inclination—smaller than an F star.

4.3 Conclusions

At present, our understanding of exoplanet atmospheres is at a tipping point. The catalogue of exoplanet transmission spectra has grown dramatically in the past few years, and the successful deployment of the *James Webb Space Telescope* has greatly expanded our resolution for studies of smaller and more distant planets. Further, future missions such as ESA's *Ariel* mission will contribute to the rapid expansion of our catalog of exoplanet atmosphere spectra. Within the midst of this growth, it is critical to ensure that spectra taken of exoplanet atmospheres represent the actual composition of the planet's atmosphere, and do not contain outside contamination such as the transit light source effect. The work done in this thesis emphasizes the plausibility of stellar activity contaminating spectra previously considered uncontaminated, introduces a method that we can use to check other pre-existing spectra for contamination, and provides a framework for future studies of transiting exoplanets that may be impacted faculae.

As the field moves closer towards characterizing the atmospheres of terrestrial planets, smaller active regions could have a significant effect in the observed transmission spectra of these tiny planets. As such, we need precision photometry, RV measurements, and activity indicators of the host stars in order to constrain any potential contamination from stellar activity. Doing so will help ensure that all observations taken of transmission spectra will truly reflect the compositions of these distant terrestrial worlds.

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